

LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS OF OFFICERS AND MEMBERS OF ACCREDITED STUDENT ORGANIZATIONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEI'S)

EMERITA T. GENEROSO

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7779-1838>

generosomerit22@gmail.com

Batangas State University

Pablo Borbon Campus, Rizal Avenue, Batangas City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Involvement in student organizations have great impact on the development of the competencies among student officers and members. This study determined the practices and competencies of student officers and members in the conduct of student organizations activity. Differences on the extent of manifestation of competencies to officers and members were also assessed. Issues and concerns of student organization in HEI's in conducting activities were further identified. The descriptive method of research was adapted through the use of a researcher – made questionnaire complemented by interviews and focus group discussion. Respondents were 72 advisers including heads and coordinators and 194 student officers which include the president, secretary and treasurer only. Weighted mean, frequency, percentage and t –test was utilized as statistical tools to treat gathered data. The findings revealed that on the activities conducted by student organizations in HEI's, orientation program was identified as the most common activity conducted by student organizations. On the other hand, conducting field trip is the least activity identified. On the practices of student organization in the conduct of the activity planning and implementation are applied greatly by advisers and officers while practices in monitoring and evaluation are moderately applied. Moreover, with regards to the competencies of officers and members' interpersonal relationship and effective communication are the topmost competencies. Advisers and officers have similar assessment relative to the practices of student organization and the manifestation of competencies in officers and members. Student organizations are more on concerned on participation and support of members in every activity and availability of funds for different activities. Lastly the proposed management plan includes activities that can be conducted to further enhance the leadership potential of officers and members of accredited student organizations in HEI's.

Keywords: Leadership Development, Management Practices, Leadership Competency, Student Activities